

B025 Calibration Flight 2nd July 2004 (16 POB max)

* Mission Scientist	Paul Field
Mission Scientist	John Methven
Mission Scientist	n/a
* Flight Manager	Maureen Smith
Peroxide	n/a
Formaldehyde	n/a
FWVS	n/a
PTr-MS	Anne Hulse y - need power on at 0600 assuming
PERCA 1	Alex Parker n
PERCA 2	Mark Jacob n
NOxy	Dave Stewart n -
AMS	n/a
ORAC / PAN	n/a
WAS	n/a
NPL-TDLAS	Will Flynn n
Core Chemistry	n/a
FAGE	Trevor Ingham x
Pilot	Alan Roberts - training
* Pilot	Alan Foster - Examier
* Co-Pilot	Mark Robinson
* FTE/CCM	Gaynor Ottaway
CCM 2	Doug Anderson ✓

POB = 13

University staff = 7 ok

* Instrument pre-flight Steve Devereau

* essential for flight to take place

Aircraft Power	0700 L
Science Brief	0930 L
Take Off	1130 L

0800 brief

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...025...

Date ...2.7.04.....

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Video Tapes
(V8)
No.
Ends
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	52°12.46N	52°12.46N
Long	0°10.33E	0°10.35E
Time	092835	092913
Status	✓	ALIGN

DRS	☒
HORACE	☒
SATCOM	☐

not sending messages p/f.

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
095311	INU to	Navigate	made:					
110104	TAKE OFF	FROM	CAMBRIDGE					
114853	Tail de-icing	ON	to clear	FFC	windew			
1205	SW de-icing	OFF	→	struggling	to clear	ice (OAT = -2°C)!		
121453	rewind	FFC	tape	+ restart	recording			
	Request	QNH	= 1005	/1006				
Power drawn:	28V: 0.8	KVA,	230V: 4.8	KVA				
	200V: Red	2A,	Yellow	1A,	Blu: 10A			
Gen 1: 48A	Gen 2: 30A							
160227	LAND	AT	CAMBRIDGE		5hrs.			
			GPS Shutdown	posn.				
			52°12.56N					
			0°10.45E					

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B025 2.7.04

Instruments

1. NEV2 - TWC sensor not responding to cal input after t/o.
Balance needle on max hot all the time, para 213 NVTC = 0 DCSU
Collector = -1.24V
After landing - noticed twc collector wire broken.
2. Satcom.c - queuing messages but not sending them (vrb 1152...
GPS showing speed = 3 Kts
reset CB at 1200, speed now 20kts! course = 000 (should be 177°)
or 180
posn and alt correct though.
started working at 1320 + sending backlog of messages.

3. AMT4 - usual problem with display disappearing during p/f
in flight all leds flashing at once in

4. h-zip - zip warning: could not open for reading h-javascript.log
lots of times
zip warning - could not open for rdy TCP/IP & FTP server.log:76
adding TCP/IP & RE>CCRUN.LOG; 591
H-zip aborted

5. CorCon - aft o/b monitor, picture disappeared

FAAM Notes: Have been asked to show crews how to use SATCOM H Tel so that they can send an Ops Normal call to base every now.

Aircraft

- Background hiss on VHF2 constantly
- Headset missing from CorCon - fore
- i/c on ORAC/PAN rack v/s.
- 2300kg fuel on landing

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 025

Date 2-7-04

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
Navigation			Cloud Physics		
INU		/	Probes		
GPS		/	FFSSP	X	
Satcom C		/	PCASP	X	
Satcom H		/	2D-P	X	
Thermometers			2D-C	X	
De-Iced Temp		/	Cloudscope	X	
Non De-Iced		/	SID 1	X	
Heimann		/	SID 2	X	
Hygrometers			CPI		
G. Eastern		/	HVPS		
J. Williams		/	Racks:		
Nezvorov		/	INC	X	
TWC	X		CCN / CNC / FWVS	✓	FWVS only
FWVS		✓	CVI	X	
Radiometers			Aerosol		
Upper Clear		/	PSAP	/	X
“ Red		/	Nephelometer	/	X
“ Silicon JND		/	AMS	✓	✓
“ JO1D		/			
Lower Clear		/			
“ Red		/			
“ Silicon JND		/			
“ JO1D		/			
Large Radiometers					
TAFTS	X				
MARSS	X				
DEIMOS	X				
ARIES	X				
SWS / SHIM	X				
Chemistry					
Ozone		/			
ECGC		/			
NOX		/			
CO		/	Others:		
ORAC		/			
PAN		/			
PERCA		/			
WAS		/			

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

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